

D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology

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Executive Summary

This document provides a suggested methodology for the exploration of Future Outlooks. The term itself is ambiguous. It is given meaning by embedding it as a specific process in the overall Foresight methodology being adapted by the Foresight in each of the 12 regions of the project.

The document starts by describing the work done so far or currently underway in each of the regions. By describes the remaining work that to be done, in order to complete the production of the Foresight package, namely the Foresight Vision, Action Plan and Roadmap, whose implementation will be following by WP6.

Based on this framework, the Future Outlooks methodology has its place in the development of the action plan. It involves the creation of scenarios representing regional programs for growth and development to be implemented by appropriate agents of the public sector. It concludes with the selection of scenarios that are in some sense deemed to be “optimal.”

One of the innovative aspects of this approach is the use the development of Future Outlooks as a laboratory for experimenting with the application of System Dynamic Modelling. The expectation is that this will improve understanding by stakeholders of the dynamics of regional socio-economic systems, the mutual interactions between measures, the way they evolve over time and their impact on the region as measured by key performance indicators.

It is hoped that this will lead to fuller participation by stakeholders in decision making related to the design of programs for regional growth and development.

The application of this methodology relies on the use of accompanying tools and resources, some of which have already been developed, many of which will be developed in the coming months. These include:

- The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change
- The Guides to Deep Dives on
 - COVID-19,
 - The Green Deal,
 - CAP reform,
 - The role of Biodiversity in rural economies,
- The Inventory of policy options.

They include key project deliverables of WP5, in particular those dealing with the application of SDM, represented by deliverables D5.1-5, the software tools and datasets to which these refer as well as the alpha- and beta- three-layer SDM models described later on in this text.

1 The Role of Foresight in the POLIRURAL Project

The development of Future Outlooks is an important step in each of the 12 regional Foresight exercises of the POLIRURAL project. For our purposes, the exploration of future outlooks based on the use of scenarios, corresponds to the exploration of policy options to achieve specific goals, or address specific challenges that feature in the action plan, an essential output of the Foresight process. In particular, this work provides a laboratory in which to test the use of system dynamic modelling, as a way for comparing different policy options.

Before delving into the methodology however, it is useful recall the overall goal of the project, how this will be achieved and what we have learned since we started.

One of the goals of the POLIRURAL project is to explore the phenomenon of “new entrants” as a factor in the sustainable growth and development of rural economies. The approach taken is based on a series of 12 regional Foresight initiatives, in the EU and neighbourhood countries.

The regional Foresight exercises are run as independent exercises. Each is driven by the specific needs of each region. In each case the process and sequence of events are based on a schedule determined by local conditions in collaboration with major stakeholders. The goal is that each of the 12 exercises will produce a **Vision, Action Plan, and Roadmap** that is:

- **endorsed** by major stakeholders in the economic and social life of the region, and
- **adopted** by major actors in regional administration, who will ensure the execution of the action plan and the realization of the vision, based on the timing laid out in the roadmap.

Each of these Foresight exercises is intended to provide a realistic environment in which to explore:

- concepts such as “**new entrants**” to the rural regional economies,
- related concepts such as “**rural attractiveness**,”
- the use of **Text Mining** as a productivity tool in the execution of regional Foresight, and
- the use of **System Dynamic Modelling** as a tool for stakeholder engagement and learning by diverse groups about the dynamics of complex socio-economic systems.

1.1 Integrating Project Findings on New Entrants into the Foresight Process

One of the early findings of the project include the observation that an exclusive focus on new entrant farmers would not be productive, as the sustainability of new farming activities will rely on the dynamism and vigour of other aspects of the rural economy. So, any plan to attract new farmers to a region, is unlikely to provide a formula for growth unless that plan is “completed” with plans to develop complementary aspects of the economy. A further issue has come into play and that is the impact of the pandemic on rural economies. Among other things this has meant an increase in the movement of people from urban to rural areas, as well as an increase in the practice of working from home. For these reasons we find it necessary to embed an exploration of new entrants to farming into a broader picture of new entrants and new modes of working and living in rural economies, of which farming is only a

part. This requires a broader, more holistic view of the rural economy, which is in fact consistent with modern calls for a more "systemic" approach based on more comprehensive engagement with stakeholders. In this sense our interest in new entrants has grown to include:

- New entrants to farming,
- New entrants to any other economic activity in rural areas,
- New behavioural trends such as working from home (WFH) and entrepreneurs seeking lower rents,
- New institutional actors having a transformational effect on rural economies.

Other areas of economic activity of relevance for rural areas, include such as tourism and leisure, energy, manufacturing, carbon farming and circular economy activities which share their supply chains with urban areas.

New institutional actors of relevance for us include private equity actors that may have entered rural economies to buy-up distressed assets on behalf of the big-food, energy, tourism and voluntary markets for carbon and natural capital.

1.2 Integrating Project Findings on Rural Attractiveness into the Foresight Process

A further observation concerns our interest in the concept of "rural attractiveness." In earlier stages of the project, attempts were made to derive a universal concept of rural attractiveness. What we found in the end was that this was not only difficult, but arguably ill advised. It now seems better to allow regions to develop their own concept (or concepts) of rural attractiveness, that is (are) adapted to their own sense of self and identify, their own set of values and coherent with the general purpose of the foresight exercise.

1.3 The Role of Future Outlooks in the POLIRURAL Model of Foresight

Outlooks should have changed since 2019:

- Increased urgency given by the EU and many members states to the transition to net-zero, reflected in the adoption of more ambitious targets for 2030;
- The impact of COVID on the structure of local economies, and as a catalyst for accelerated change on the adoption of policies for resilience;
- Supported by the €1.8T financial commitment which explicitly links COVID recovery to the Green Deal and the achievement of targets related to the journey to net-zero;
- The EU biodiversity strategy as a step towards implementing the wedding-cake model of sustainability, as an opportunity to create new sources of income for farmers based on the rational provision of eco-system services;
- The new freedoms offered by CAP reform to change the economic model of rural areas in favour of farming communities, farm-households, and farm-based businesses.

2 Work Leading up the Exploration of Future Outlooks

So far in the Foresight Process teams have been advised to proceed in phases as follows:

2.1 Issues Analysis

This is a process whereby we reflect on the present and recent past and consider the problems that needs to be solved or corrected for, and the issues that have arisen, in the broadest sense. This includes the consideration of issue with living and working, quality of life, the experience of democracy, the quality of public services and the functioning of public administration. Anything can be considered, but special attention should be given to those issues that may require a policy response. In this project the formal issues analysis has been restricted to a needs-analysis based on surveys and desk work conducted in WP4. It is possible to go much further than this, but in practice, one must always consider how much time and resources to devote to this exercise, based on some initial idea of the kind of results one expects to find and its relevance to the overall purpose of the Foresight exercise. In particular, the issues analysis is a good opportunity to think about “the system” and how well it works, and the possible need for “corrective.”

2.2 Drivers' Analysis

This is the real start of the Foresight exercise, in the sense that when carried out effectively, it focuses on the future. Its role is to help stakeholders understanding how change happens, what is driving change, what factors can be influenced or even amplified and what factors can only be born or mitigated. It has an arcane vocabulary that refers to trends, micro-trends, macro-trends, and mega-trends. The idea is not only to understand trends, but their dynamics and the possibility that they may change. Drivers' analysis refers to trend-breaks, and game-changers. A good drives' analysis embodies an attitude of wanting to construct the future by influencing trends, rather than simply standing by, and letting them happen. When regional managers or the citizens they serve notice an unfavourable demographic or unemployment trend, the natural response should be to arrest that trend, or even reverse it. Other examples include climate change, resource scarcity and the recent COVID-19 pandemic. These correspond to trends that pose an existential threat to groups if not to the whole of humanity and which must be reversed. The tools to do are the tools of public policy, and the choice of what policy to implement, is itself conditioned by other trends. Drivers' analysis is an opportunity to develop some shared insights into key trends that will impact your region and how the positive and negative impacts will cascade through society and the economy (the system) to affect various groups and in different aspects of their lives. To make sure that each team carries out the necessary preparations for an adequate analysis of the drivers affecting their region, we organized the production of an inventory of global drivers, based on a sharing of effort by the teams of the 12 POLIRURAL pilots. This document entitled “A STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change” is available on the project website.

Building upon the results of the issues analysis, the drivers' analysis should lead to a preliminary list of the major challenges that need to be addressed for the future growth and development of the region.

The inventory refers to 64 drives of change. A region might decide that 10 of these are of the highest relevance and importance for the region in the next 10 or 20 years. They might then rationalize this by structuring them in some way, motivated by an overview of the economy, guided by the values of the region and its sense of identity, and informed by concepts of rural attractiveness that may as yet be only half-formed or emergent, and which may not take final form until the vision building process draws to an end.

2.3 Performing Deep Dives and Defining the Policy Challenges

The purpose of such exercises is to explore in more depth various aspects of what has been learned so far. The team might have decided that climate change is a major drive of change and even a game-changer for the region but may not yet understand how it has played out so far at regional level, or how this might evolve in the near future. Every region is different, and the same trend may be positive for one region or very negative for another. The deep dive is needed to get to grips with what this driver or factor really means for the region and is an essential part of the preparation needed to decide what to do about it. Climate change is such an important issue nowadays that it is hard to imagine a Foresight exercise being conducted at regional level without a deep dive on climate change, and an effort to really understand what is going on.

In general, it is not possible to conduct a useful deep dive without the involvement of experts. So, the organizing teams of the regional Foresight initiatives really need to get on the phone and contact people with expert knowledge about the subject, in particular about how it manifests itself in your region, and how likely to continue, get better or worse. It is essential to work with local experts, not only to help separate the facts from the fantasies of local conspiracy theorists, but also to bring on board stakeholders that will lend credibility to any eventual analysis you produce and point the way towards the kind of robust high-quality datasets and other evidence that serious policy initiative nowadays require.

Climate change is one of the great drivers of change of our time. It is driving change among consumers and the behaviours of ordinary people in every age-group, the strategies of companies both big and small, the activities of shareholders, and investors, as well as the policies of governments at nation, region, and city level, so it is important to understand what it means specifically in your region and for your ongoing Foresight exercise. But this is the obvious one, other drivers are also of importance, but they are more recent and are therefore at risk of being overlooked. These include:

- CAP reform,
- The EU Biodiversity Strategy,
- The COVID-19 pandemic,
- The COVID recovery package in the form of the Green Deal.

Anyone who reads the occasional newspaper will be aware of these, but they may not have “connected the dots” or fully internalize their significance for regional economies, so we are providing a series of guides to deep dives, based on starting strategic conversations on these four subjects.

It is not necessary for each of the POLIRURAL pilots to carry out deep-dives on each of these four topics. But they should consider doing so. They may decide to carry out deep-dives on a different set of topics, for example on the key challenges identified as part of the output of their Drivers' Analysis. Ultimately, they must decide for themselves, based on what is best for their region and in consultations with their major stakeholders, in particular with those that will endorse the final "package" and bear the burden of monitoring progress once the final "package" has been adopted.

We have already provided a guide based on the impact of COVID, and the other three will come soon. The deep-dive methodology is the same in each case. Based on these four examples, it is expected that the regional teams should be able to adapt the approach to any subject they care to address.

2.4 Building the Vision

Having completed a series of deep-dives and having revised or refined the list of key challenges that will drive future growth and development, the Foresight teams and their stakeholders will have grown considerably in their knowledge and understanding of the region, and its potential. Enough to start forming a general picture of what the region should feel like at some suitably distant time in the future. A time that is often called the "time-horizon" or "landing point" for the Foresight exercise. At this point, some of those involved in each team should start thinking about a vision statement that will become an important part of the overall Foresight package for the region.

If someone starts to have thoughts along the lines of their region becoming "the number one producer of potassium," alarm bells should start to ring. Such a goal might be highly desirable, but it only amounts to an ambition and does correspond to what we mean by a vision. So, you need to be careful about the difference between missions, ambitions, and visions.

A vision statement is essentially a communication tool. It needs to be aspirational. It should be consistent with the action plan, and in this sense, it is hard to nail down until the action plan is clear and well understood.

It should also be consistent with the values of those who espouse it. Also, with their sense of identity, their sense of purpose as a people.

Many prescriptions exist for creating visions. Each has its adherents. But I suggest a process such as the following, to be modified or adapted by each regional team as they see fit.

Depending on the time and resources available, it is worth combining a number of brainstorming sessions such as the following:

- To consider pre-existing visions of the region or similar regions, with a view to discussing what your stakeholders like or don't like about the vision, what it captures, what it misses, with a view to deciding what shape your own vision should take.

- To explore one's own value system. What are those values. To what extent are they representative of their region and the people who live there, the people it would like to attract?
- To explore one's own sense of purpose. What is it or what are they? To what extent are they representative of their region and the people who live there, the people it would like to attract?
- To identify individual words or phrases or concepts that should figure in your vision statement.

One of the interesting issues to arise in the context of the POLIRURAL project is the role of concepts of attractiveness. On that basis it seems useful to add to the list of brainstorming options above, a brainstorming session on "attractiveness" intended to crystalize the concept and see how to integrate concepts of attractiveness into the overall vision statement.

These exercises can be done remotely or in groups sitting around a table, in plenary or in break out mode. The break-out mode allows small groups to working independently and often results in a variety of different philosophies being exposed. The breakout sessions can come-together and compare notes and try to make a synthesis.

However, each team decides to do this, it is useful to start with discussions of principle, and collect lists of concepts or ideas that you agree as a group that should somehow come through in the final vision statement.

Armed with all of this preparatory work, you can then set about crafting a 3- to 5- line, or even 10-line vision statement. There are many ways to do this. You might

- Give the job to one person, and present the results to a group for discussion and refinement,
- Give the job to several volunteers, and present the results to the bigger group for discussion and refinement,
- Give the job to a small number of teams working on their own independent versions of the vision and bring them together at some point to see the difference and motivate a discussion about how to bring these different ideas together and develop a new version of the vision that more fully captures the "collective."

I have often organized this based on two meetings.

- An initial one where we combine morning sessions devoted to the preliminary brainstorming, followed up with an afternoon sessions where we develop an initial vision.
- A break before the next sessions, where we sit on this early version of the vision for several months while we are busy with tasks related to the action plan and roadmap.
- A final session where we come back. For example, one could use a morning session to recall the results of the preliminary work, the progress made on the action plain and finish off with a final session to review and improve the vision. It is possible to do this with a main "author" editing a document on-screen, and a moderator who holds the mic and walks among those present in the offline plenary.

As you can see, there are many ways to do this. Each regional team will decide what is best for them, based on the time and resource available, as well as on any other social engineering goals they might have in mind. Such discussions can have an important impact on the identification of challenges and the structure of the action plan. So, the journey from an action plan to a vision is not a linear one. It is a loop or an iterative process, where discussions on the action plan, lead to refinements of the vision, leading to adjustments to the list of challenges and modifications of the action plan.

3 Exploring Future Outlooks

3.1 Understanding Policy Options

The exploration of policy options requires an understanding of policies and the many ways in which policy measures are formulated and delivered. For this reason, it is essential to involve people from regional agencies and departments of public administration. Even though it is their job to know about their things, like anyone in professional life, their knowledge will not be perfect, and they may be happy to take part in this part of the Foresight exercise if it affords an opportunity to update their knowledge or even to meet peers whose experience is different from theirs.

Most importantly, it is essential to involve these people in the exploration of policy options, because they are the ones who may be charged with following up on the implementation of these options. From this point of view, their participation provides an opportunity to inject realism, manage expectations, understand the realistic timelines involved in implementations and shape things in ways that make their work and the expected results more achievable.

The method for exploring policy options is fairly simple and straightforward. The main input is the list of major challenges to be addressed in order to realize the “vision.” This list is based on:

- the Issues Analysis (in our case the needs analysis of WP4)
- the Drivers’ Analysis
- the Deep-Dives,
- further refinements based on the work involved in the elaboration of the vision.

The final list may contain 2 to 5 challenges. The main task now is to transform each challenge into a list of 2 to 10 measures needed to adequately address that challenge.

Ideally each of these measures should be justified by the provision of an “intervention logic” and characterized by a set of KPIs.

3.1.1 Creating the Inventory of Policy Options

Most stakeholders will know or understand little of policy and the details of how to make it happen. Nevertheless, it is very important to involve them in the elaboration of the action plan. They may not contribute much to the initial design of measures, but their most valuable contribution may be in their reactions to proposals, the identification of gaps, and in particular in the identification of gaps that can easily be filled in order to accommodate the needs of specific groups or minorities. Such issues can often be addressed at the early design stage, at no extra cost. Whereas attempts to “hack” existing solutions or extend established programs as an afterthought may be costly and disruptive.

The rate of experimentation and creative endeavour in public policy has increased considerably over the years. Not only at local level, but also in terms of the scaling of innovative pilot concepts, and in terms of the financing of programs and projects. That is the good news. The bad news is that this creates a challenge for policy experts who want to keep

up with “good practice.” For this reason, we will follow the same approach as for the drivers’ analysis and prepare an “inventory of policy options” that the teams can use as a support for their work.

This will be prepared as with the drivers’ inventory, on the basis of a sharing of work by the 12 regional teams. The structure of this document is not finalized. It will contain sections on access to land, the urban-rural nexus, carbon farming and the provision of ecological services, rural energy systems and the circular economy, as well as the transition to net-zero. Arguably the most innovative part of this inventory will be a section on finance. The bottom line is that no significant measure gets done without money, and unless the method of financing is identified in advanced the plan is likely to remain at best an interesting document and never pass into legislation.

3.1.2 Clarifying the Intervention Logic

It is important to explain the “intervention logic.” This is a good opportunity to involve experts in the Foresight process since most stakeholders will not be experts. They may have good general knowledge or awareness of issues and opinions on specific policy options, but their understanding will generally be fragmented and in need to qualification or completion by experts. It is also important that the team preparing events where the stakeholders will meet to explore options, will adequately prepare the stakeholders for taking part in these meetings, in particular by developing and circulating background papers that gathering together a range of policy options, drawn from examples of measures that have been implemented in other regions of Europe or from other parts of the world. Such documents have been described many times in the POLIRURAL project, referred to by the generic title of Curated Reading Lists of CRLs, and their production based on the use of Semex, a text mining tool, has been an important focus on the work on Text Mining in the project.

The exploration of possible policy measures should involve a discussion of the intervention logic. From a practical point of view, this means a narrative linking the measure to other measures in the policy mix and to the overall policy challenge or challenges to which it is expected to provide a solution, and thereby filling in details as to how the measure will contribute to achieving the vision. One can also refer to this intervention logic as a “Theory of Change.” There is some ambiguity in the use of the term, due to the existence of a literature that treats the theory of change, as a theory of institutions and other “power structures” and which ones need to be mobilized, demobilized, or appeased so that the desired changes can effectively happen.

This kind of institutional intelligence is also often created (or co-created) on the basis of what is called Review of Institutional Arrangements (RIA). In the case of the POLIRURAL pilots, this work is being taken care of in other ways, for example based on the involvement of appropriate stakeholders in specific events of the Foresight process and supported by an Inventory of Policy Measures, which contains lists sources of funding for policy measures and identifies the centers of power in local administration that have the competence or responsibility for programming based on those sources of finance.

The development and codification of the intervention logic, in the context of the 12 regional Foresight initiatives of the POLIRURAL project, is based on what is referred to as a logframe

(or logical framework). This provides a way for rationalizing how a mixture of policy measures combine to produce multiple “outputs,” “impacts” and “outcomes” as represented in the following diagram (Figure 1).

The “THEORY of CHANGE” is all about how these different “steps” are linked to each other. Usually, it is not explicitly written down. It always exists even if only half understood. Learning through evaluation helps you improve by updating your “theory of change” ...

Figure 1 Theory of Change diagram

This may sound rather abstract, and a bit overwhelming, but to make it more accessible, one can take the example of “training” as a measure to address unemployment or job-quality.

Measures	Training courses, characterized method, topic, length, type of trainer...
Outputs	The number of people successfully trained...
Outcomes	The number of newly qualified people ready for work and in the job market
Impacts	The number of people employed with those qualifications

This is not an exact science, by any means, and there are other ways of looking at the same thing. For example, one could also propose the following logframe for the same measures.

Measures	Training courses, characterized method, topic, length, type of trainer...
Outputs	The number of people successfully trained and ready for work
Outcomes	The number of people employed with those qualifications
Impacts	The expansion of a major employer based on suitably qualified personnel

It is not possible to say one is better than the other.

The first case reflects a concern for employment and getting people into jobs. The Impact statement is clearly about people in new jobs. The narrative describing the intervention logic might start with a story about the levels of unemployment, an analysis of the overall job market, and an examination of trends related to future skill needs. The measures related to “training” might involve the recruitment of new staff at local training institutes and the creation of new courses with the details left up to the new professors.

The second case reflects a concern for the HR needs of major employers. Typically, big companies that might expand given the right conditions, whose expansion will create a demand for a certain kind of a work force. The measures include training co-delivered by local training institution and the companies, based on curricula whose development is overseen by skills’ councils involving key personnel from the interested companies. These may organize recruitment days and internships and donate tools and other resources to the training institute.

Talking through the intervention logic is an opportunity to deepen and enrich the overall understanding of the goal or desired impact of the measures undertaken. It provides an opportunity to check on what really needs to be done to reach this goal, and it sets the stage for an adult conversation about the cost of the initiative, the time scale for the intervention and the choice of indicators needed to monitor progress in achieving that goal.

Ideally each step in the program logic can be monitored with the use of KPIs, as suggested below based on the “training” measures example (Figure 2).

The “LOGICAL FRAMEWORK” has its origins in work of USAID in the 1970s. Many funding agencies have progressively built upon this since then. There are many variations on the same basic ideas. The main insights relate to how best to use this framework.

Program Logic	Comment	Indicators
INPUTS	Everything needed to implement a program of activities, ideally broken down by activity ...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budgets • The HR effort of agencies and ministries • The HR effort of internal + external experts • Other inputs (fees, PPP investment...)
ACTIVITIES (MEASURES)	All relevant things done that are part of the mission of an organization, or described in a contract with a service provider, i.e., training programs ...	Everything to do with the formal or professional planning and monitoring of activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget expenditure ... • On time execution of tasks ...
OUTPUTS	The formal deliverables promised by each activity, often (but not always) described in a contract ...	This too is often described in a contract: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of people trained ... • The number successfully qualified ...
OUTCOMES	If training is an output, this is only a means to an end. This end is the “outcome” of the activity. For example, it might be employment or promotion and better wages...	For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of graduates who find a job within three months ... • The number of graduates who move on to higher paying work ...
IMPACTS (OBJECTIVES)	The ultimate aim of all of these efforts and the reason behind the allocated budgets is a series of ambitious goals that are the result of all of these different outcomes ...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced unemployment • Higher levels of income • Reduced welfare payments • Increased active population • Increased exports due to better export capability ...

Figure 2 Logical framework example

In reality the attention of those involved tends to be on the measures and their outputs. These often correspond to the programming period of a measure and a check on outputs is all that is needed to determine if the terms of the contracts have been respected, at which point everyone involved gets busy with something else.

As a final word, it must be said that the use of this framework is not without its detractors. In the past “experts” working on the design and implementation of development projects have experienced great difficulty in using it. In practice it provides a framework that is often applied retrospectively, as part of an evaluation activity, and not before as part of a policy or measure design process.

For our purposes, it is suggested that the regional Foresight teams adopt aspects of the overall approach as a way of structuring their thinking about measures and their selection and the construction of narratives that explain the choices that they make.

The completion of narratives of selection is best done with the help of some numbers, the indicators referred to previously. But our focus will be on the indicators of impacts. These we equate with a selection of KPIs, that measure the performance of the economy, as well as progress towards successfully addressing the policy challenges which must be met in order to realize the “vision” that embodies the overall program for growth and development which has been codified as part of the Foresight process.

3.1.3 Choosing SMART Indicators and KPIs

It is a well-established principle that what gets measured gets managed and in using the logframe, it is common to provide indicators at every level of “achievement,” at the level of outputs, outcomes, and impacts.

Providing a full set of indicators for all measures that make up the action-plan in the regional Foresight package produced in the context of the POLIRURAL project, is a lot of work, so it is suggested that the Foresight teams focus on the most important ones, the measures of “impact.” Ultimately these can be considered as indicators of performance of the local economy.

Nevertheless, the design of indicators is not as easy as it may look. Guidelines for creating indicators were provided in 1981 by George T. Doran writing in *Management Review*¹. He suggested a set of rules summarized by a SMART mnemonic. There are many variations on this and on what each letter means, but the following table captures the general idea, adapted to the needs of the POLIRURAL project.

¹ Doran, G. T. (1981). There's a SMART way to write management's goals and objectives. *Management review*, 70(11), 35-36.

S	Specific in the sense of clear and easy to understand
M	Measurable. It sounds obvious but most people will not know what data exists...
A	Achievable. It too sounds obvious, but few have a reliable “feeling” for the numbers...
R	Relevant. If a proxy is needed, its relevance should be explained
T	Time-bound in the sense that it should be clear by when the indicator is to be achieved

The diagram provided above (Figure 1) outlining the Theory of Change, is intended to reflect the reality that policy challenges often hide a lot of complexity and that combinations of measures are required in order for these challenges to be addressed. Different measures act on the region in different ways, over different periods of time. The phasing of measures, the order in which they are executed, is important. Different measures in the mix may complement each other in different ways and the impacts may happen with a delay in that a typical measure can be expected to provide an impact that will unfold over years, for example over periods of 3 to 10 years. These are all issues that will not be obvious to typical stakeholders taking part in the Foresight process. They may not even be obvious to the policy experts taking part. It is therefore reasonable to ask if tools exist for use in the context of a Foresight process, that will help stakeholders better understand the implications of the policy choices made, their interactions, and how their impact might emerge over time.

One of the ambitions of the POLIRURAL project is to explore the use of SDM (System Dynamic Modelling) as a tool to better understand the dynamics of the policy-measure mix, the way in which different measures interact with each other over time, conspiring to “impact” the KPIs that characterize the performance of the regional economy, and that reflect progress in addressing the corresponding policy challenge.

For many people, the discussion on indicators is not very interesting. It seems a bit technical and some may want to “leave it up to the experts.” Nevertheless, there is a lot to be learned from working through a process of indicator design. Indeed, there is everything to be gained, by making sure that the indicators are indeed SMART and that they do provide a basis for monitoring progress on the implementation of the action plan. In particular, the involvement of stakeholders in the design of indicators, will ensure that the final set avoids ambiguity and obfuscation and reflects the interests of minority groups, where appropriate.

A well-crafted action plan will include a process for monitoring progress on implementing, typically by setting up a monitoring committee composed of a representative set of stakeholders and led by powerful organisations capable of holding local government to account, as well as a budget to facilitate tasks such as interim evaluations and mid-course adjustments to the action plan where needed.

3.2 Crafting Future Outlooks

In summary, the development of the theory of change and the process of establishing clear targets for the KPIs, provides a platform for the selection of an “optimal” set of policy measures.

The exploration of “future outlooks” is part of the overall Foresight process intended to produce a set of measures needed to fully address one or more of the policy challenges identified earlier in the Foresight, which must be addressed in order to achieve the growth and development needed to realize the foresight vision.

It is unlikely that the initial list of policy challenges and equally, initial lists of policy measures deemed necessary to address those challenges will be adequate or complete. As the work goes on, understanding will increase, especially with the increased involvement of experts. It is likely that as this understanding grows, the description of measures will be enriched, the need for new measures may be recognized and even the need to define new challenges that need to be addressed in order to realize the vision.

Practically, this means that one considers lists of challenges and measures as “work in progress” and be ready to revise these by adding new elements or tweaking their definition as the process goes on.

Intelligence, creativity and an open mind are essential to achieving a good result. The burden of effort in this falls upon the shoulders of the regional Foresight team. They must work to preserve this openness and assume the work of updating the “lists” as new insights arise and as greater understanding emerges of the true nature of the challenges to be addressed.

The process is deliberate and slow to allow time for these changes to occur, and arrive at an action plan that is adequate, in that it includes all of the measures needed to succeed. As a simple example, the promotion of regional tourism may require a range of measures such as the development of infrastructure, the training of people to work in the sector, and the provision of incentives that will encourage entrepreneurial activity, festivals, events, and other activities that tourists coming to the region might enjoy. But the development of the sector may also require more commercially oriented tasks related to regional marketing, and communication, some of which can be done by commercial actors which may need training if they are to do this well, along with efforts led by local government or business associations on behalf of sector and the region. It is easy to overlook the big picture and neglect to reserve budget for the fully program needed for success. Best results are obtained with an iterative process in which the Foresight team loops on a process of listing measures, consulting with stakeholders on their adequacy, reviewing the program with local experts, comparing this with what is being done elsewhere, will lead to better results. Not only does the local Foresight team need to impose this kind of discipline on the process, to avoid what could later amount to unfortunate omissions, it also needs to decide when the process has gone far enough, and bring it to close, respecting the deadlines imposed by circumstance and timing constraints imposed by local policy and programming cycles.

The “future outlooks” are scenarios based on:

- A list of policy measures intended to address one or more policy challenges;
- A set of narratives describing the intervention logic;
- A set of KPIs intended to track progress in addressing the policy challenge;
- A listing of the current values of those KPIs and their expected values to realize the vision.

These future outlooks can be compared to determine which ones are in some sense “optimal.”

Optimization is a vague concept and what it means in practice will depend very much on the tools made available. In principle one can talk of the “preferred future outlook” as an optimal mix at the level of the vision, each individual challenge, or each individual measure. It could refer to the expected values of indicators assigned to outputs, outcomes, or impacts. It could refer to expected cumulative impact ten years out, break-even in 5 years’ time, or value-for-money ten years out. The tools for doing this are underdeveloped, to the extent that they even exist.

In reality, most Foresight actions will deal with optimization in a very qualitative manner, by simply ranking options on a purely qualitative basis using the “collective intelligence” of opinion of stakeholders using a simple one- or two- criteria ranking using post-its and a ready surface for display.

- A one-criterion ranking could be based on an intuitive concept of “best”, to be decided after a “levelling up” discussion to make sure that there is a shared understanding of the scenarios to be ranked.
- A two-criterion ranking process might be preferable in that it tries to deal with trade-offs. Such a process might proceed by assigned to each scenario a score based on arbitrary scales assigning a score to reflect each stakeholder view on things like “impact,” “time-frame for delivery,” or “cost of implementation.”

The POLIRURAL project aims at exploring the use of System Dynamic Modelling, to support parts of the overall Foresight process.

3.3 The Role of SDM in Exploring Future Outlooks

In the early stages of the Foresight initiatives, most of the emphasis was in the participation of stakeholders considered local beneficiaries, effectively the “owners” of the issues or challenges that would need to be addressed on the basis of mixtures of policy interventions... Now the emphasis moves decidedly towards the involvement of the policy professionals. They are ones who know how to get things done. They will “take over” in the sense that they will ensure the mobilization of funds and the implementation of the measures that make up the action plan.

3.3.1 The Challenge of Embedding SDM as Part of the Foresight Process

One of the important goals of the POLIRURAL project is to explore the use of System Dynamic Modelling in Foresight. The project starts with no predefined idea as to how this should be done and the need to maintain an open mind as to the possibilities this presents is very clear. Software exists to support the authoring of interactive models and this provides the possibility that the Foresight process will allow:

- The authoring of general models that somehow capture the complex dynamics of the socio-economic and environmental systems of interest to the stakeholders;
- The editing of such models to reflect the specificity of the regions being modelled, their specific state of development and the overall goals of the Foresight exercise;
- The use of such models to explore policy options, the impact of mixtures of policy measures on the system.

This has posed a challenge for the project on several levels, notably:

- The lack of models that reflect the realities of regional development, in particular that reflect the real dynamics of rural regions,
- The fact that existing tools (such as STELLA) employ concepts and representation so those concepts (based on “stocks” and “flows”) which are non-intuitive and far removed from the language and ideas employed by those interested in development,
- The high level of effort required to develop and adapt interfaces for use by non-experts in the use of the tool.
- The need to experiment with such tools in a context of a real Foresight exercise, whose success cannot be comprised by the uncertainties and necessary risks attending the exploratory development of innovative Foresight techniques based on the use of such tools.

In summary, the task of experimenting with the use of such tools in Foresight requires action on each of these levels:

- The development of suitable general models,
- Capable of being edited to accommodate the needs and interests of different regions,
- Their presentation via an interface which is meaningful to and navigable by a wide range of users from different backgrounds, perhaps accompanied by suitably trained “guides,”
- Their use to explore the dynamics of rural regions in ways that support the overall Foresight process and the production of the Foresight package, made up of a Vision, Action Plan and Roadmap.

3.3.2 Initial Efforts

Our initial idea was to use SDM as a tool to support interactive group-work in the Drivers’ Analysis phase of the Foresight Process. This idea was based on an expectation that it might be possible to more rigorously present and explore the dynamics of change to the rural systems, as a “next step” following on from the enumeration of lists of drivers using standard techniques such as STEEPV. This approach was abandoned once it was realized that it would require a lot of work, in addition to the enumeration of drivers, to:

- define what is being driven,
- translate this into the arcane SDM vocabulary of stocks and flows,
- find relevant data sets,
- test and calibrate the models, and
- develop and test suitable interfaces.

Finally, the exploration of the impact of external factors on the system requires the creation of a model in layers with a base layer that captures the dynamics of regions and higher layers that capture the impact of external factors on regional performance.

This remains a fascinating research project but is far too ambitious for the constraints of the POLIRURAL project.

3.3.3 A More Pragmatic Approach

The next approach was to build a mini model of the rural region, that may one day be integrated into a more “complete” model. Our main cue was taken from interest shown by

the regional Foresight teams in the diversification of the rural economy, in particular based on the specific interest shown by some regional Foresight teams in the role of rural tourism as a growth engine for rural areas.

So, the general approach evolved to one based on the building of mini-models, capable of supporting an exploration of the system dynamics of rural regions. The idea was to start with a small model capturing key aspects of the dynamics of the tourism industry, which could then be extended in various ways to capture further aspects of the dynamics of the tourism industry, including the impact of external factors, and for this work to be repeated across different sectors of the rural economy, sectors such farming, forestry, food processing, raw material processing, energy, and the circular economy.

Much work is needed to develop this picture, for example by adding the impact of the environment based on these sectors, some form of “wedding cake” model of sustainability, as well as transversal models dealing with land-use and land ownership.

Once more this is a very interesting long-term research project, that will provide challenges long after the POLIRURAL project, but it provides a manageable framework within which to explore the use of SDM in Foresight, in the context of the POLIRURAL project.

3.4 The Tourism Mini-Model

The construction of the model was carried out in two phases:

- The production of an alpha model, terminology borrowed from an old practice in IT, where the alpha model is a paper model, that captures all of its features, before any code is written. The authoring of the alpha model is something that can be done using the relatively familiar language and concepts of tourism and economic development. It avoids worrying about the technology of modelling software and the difficulties associated with building interfaces in real-life, and all of the technical challenges and compromises that those tasks necessarily involve.
- The “beta model” which involves translating this into the language of SDM, in particular the concept of stocks and flows, using the facilities provided by the STELLA software, and working with what has proven to be a poor and laborious user interface design facility.

Key design decisions followed from fixing the purpose of the model, as that of providing support for the selection of policies or which are in some sense “optimal” in their contribution to realizing the Foresight vision or addressing challenges associated with realizing attendant to the vision.

The main design constraint was to create a model in three layers.

- A top layer provided by measurable and meaningful (SMART) KPIs.
- A middle layer consisting of factors that make up the “machine” of the economy, be they drivers, enablers, barriers all of the factors referred to in the STEEPV inventory.
- A bottom layer also consisting of factors but specifically those provided by policy measures.

From a practical point of view the alpha model consists of

- A diagram with three layers showing how all of these are connected. In this sense it provides a visual representation of the system,
- An accompanying text that explains the arrows, describing the dynamics or flows that they represent. So far this has been referred to as a KDP (KPIs, Drivers and Policy options) matrix with entries providing narratives explaining the intervention logic, connecting the policy measures to the KPIs, via their impact on different aspects of the “system.”

For the specific case of the tourism mini model, the KPIs describe the performance of the tourism sector in the rural economy. The following four have been chosen:

- The number of people who visit the region as tourists,
- The number of nights they spend there,
- The amount of money they spent there,
- The number of jobs supported by their coming to the region.

The middle layer intended to capture the system, contains four major factors:

- Infrastructure
- Accommodation
- Monuments and amenities
- Activities, events, and experiences.

The third layer consists of three kinds of policy measures:

- Programs to enhance access, visibility, and awareness,
- Programs to develop needed skills and human capabilities?
- Programs to encourage tourism related entrepreneurial activity.

All of these hide lots of complexity. Visitors could refer to short stay, weekends, long stays or the total. It could refer to those who come by car, or by plane or by boat or everyone. It could refer to those who come for religious tourism, sports tourism, business tourism, youth tourism or all of the above.

Infrastructure could refer to transport and mobility, regional airports, train lines, or car parks for tour buses. It could mean public toilets and showers, trails and pathways, picnic places, seating for older people, wheelchair access, nature reserves, places of natural beauty, signage, publicly available maps and apps and websites, local tourism- or booking-offices. The same can be said of any of the 11 elements referred to in the diagram. Clearly such a model can be extended and improved in many ways. It will never be perfect, but it can be improved. The process of improvement could itself evolve into a useful form of stakeholder engagement. The latest version of the alpha model for tourism looks like on Figure 3.

Figure 3 Tourism alpha model

Such a paper model can be used as it is. In the form of a diagram that can be projected onto a wall in a room or shared on a screen in a Zoom meeting. It can provide a basis for discussion, be criticized, edited, and modified. The accompanying KDP matrix can also be discussed, edited, and modified. In principle this can help the stakeholders develop a deeper understanding of how the economy works and what measures or policy mixes are required to achieve the vision of address the related policy challenges.

The accompanying KDP matrix is as depicted on Figure 4.

The matrix provides a way for recording narratives that explain how the drivers will have an impact on the KPIs
 A-priori the KPIs are Independent Variables
 In a more detailed model they may be elaborated upon

	KPI 1: No. of Visitors to the region	KPI 2: No of Nights spent in the region	KPI 3: Spending by visitors to the region	KPI 4: Jobs created in the region
Lower limit				
Upper limit		100.000	200.000	50.000.000,00 €
D1: Infrastructure (travel, comfort, experience ...)	Airports and ports, train and bus stations make the region more accessible and easier to reach. The availability of public toilets and showers make being there more comfortable. Facilities for outdoor activities such as trails and pathways, picnic places, seating for older people, access for wheelchairs also make it more attractive... also car-parks, parks, nature reserves, places of natural beauty, signage, maps, a tourism or bookings office...			Good infrastructure creates jobs in building and maintenance, as well as in running facilities and amenities...
D2: Hotels and accommodation (no of beds available)	The presence of suitable accommodation makes the region more attractive for different categories of visitor	The number of beds and rooms creates the potential to welcome visitors who stay for more than one day...	The quality of accommodation affects the spending on this item, also the use of facilities such as conference rooms, in-house restaurants and bars... also youth hostels and camp-sites...	Accommodation creates potential for jobs in hospitality, managers and line-staff, front desk, kitchen, floor, cleaning etc.
D3: Sites, monuments and museums (no of amenities)	These make the region more attractive as a destination by giving visitors things to do	They provide incentive to stay over and experience more	They provide visitors with opportunities to spend their money in the region	They create employment for managers and line-staff, curators, performers and other service providers
D4: Events	Festivals are a great way to attract people to a region ... the numbers can range from 100s to millions over 1 million ... this needs to be built up over time ... but music festivals are not the only kinds of event ...	In some cases the family follows... medical tourism for example...	Their main impact may be on spending and catering but also on fees... the policy trick is to extend the festival season into other seasons and make full use of infrastructure and transform seasonal work into full time jobs ...	Festivals (for example) also create employment for musicians, support staff such as riggers, sound and lighting crews... Medical and sports tourism creates jobs for doctors, nurses, dieticians, trainers and physio-therapists and other specialists...
D5: Entrepreneurial Ventures	Entrepreneurs invest in events and things to do... paint-ball, sports, music and drama festivals, training camps ... clinics for medical tourism... all providing reasons to come and visit...	Entrepreneurs are required to invest in different kinds of accommodation ranging from high-end hotels to camp-sites... all enabling longer stays	Entrepreneurs are needed to invest in cafes, bars, restaurants, cinemas and concerts halls, dance festival venues... all increasing the need to stay over-night...	Jobs are created in design and construction, of buildings, interiors, experiences ... as well as for running and maintenance ...
D6: Skills	The availability of a suitable labour pool is a limiting factor on the type of accommodation available	The availability of a suitable labour pool is a limiting factor on the length of stay, due to its impact on the quality of accommodation and amenities...	The availability of a suitable labour pool is a limiting factor on spending due to its impact on the quality of opportunities for leisure and entertainment...	The availability of a suitable labour pool is a limiting factor on the job places that can be filled...
D7: Visibility and Awareness	People will only come if they know about what is going on...	They will only stay or come back if it is fun and has suitable accommodation...	Visitors will budget for the visit on the basis of anticipation of what there is to do ...	This creates feedback loops in terms of attractiveness for entrepreneurs ... who invest and create jobs...

Figure 4 A KDP matrix example

The details don't really matter for us right now; The main thing is to give an idea of the look and feel of the model and how it might be used in practice.

Some progress has been made turning this into a beta model. The main challenge related to the creation of beta-models stems from the fact that a model in STELLA looks like on Figure 5.

Figure 5 Tourism beta model made in STELLA

This is much less intuitive than the alpha-model presented earlier. The STELLA software being used to develop these models does allow one to create user interfaces, but this facility is cumbersome and limited in flexibility and it has proven a be a challenge to transform the alpha model into a user-friendly beta model.

Nevertheless, progress has been made and so far, we have experiment with specific trajectories through the alpha model diagram. For example, focusing on an intervention logic linking policy options that represent different projects to develop a regional airport, we look at the impact on airport capacity as a measure of the outcome and on the number of visitors for tourism purposes as an impact of this measure, to explore growth in the number of tourists over time and the limits to growth imposed by constraints on the capacity of the airport.

The mini model intended to capture these features of a regional tourism dynamics are based on a beta model which equates infrastructure with a regional airport, modelled simply by the number of passengers it can receive in a year. Historical data from a real airport was obtained to establish a baseline and the scenario 0 below is a simple extrapolation of this data, with a cut-off at just below full capacity. The model is completed by various assumptions about the number of rural visitors coming for tourism purposes, and the various policy measures are modelled by their impact on the ceiling for capacity. The beta-model allows the user to interact with various scenarios as follows:

- **Scenario 0:** This is the default scenario where no changes are made to improve the airport. Click on run to see how the traffic increases organically, until it reaches a maximum due to the limited capacity of the airport.

- **Scenario 1:** Airport capacity is increased by 250,000 per year, based on improvements to existing terminals, with work starting in 2021 and finishing in 2023. Click on “run” to see how this scenario will impact the number of visitors for tourism.
- **Scenario 2:** Airport capacity is increased by 1 million per year, based on the addition of an extra runway, with work starting in 2021 and finishing in 2027.
- **Scenario 3:** Airport capacity is increased by 1 million per year, based on the extension of an existing runway, with work starting in 2024 and finishing in 2030.
- **Scenario X:** Build your own scenario, using the interactive table and run it to see the impact on visitors.

After a lot of work, the interface of this mini model looks like on Figure 6.

Figure 6 Tourism mini model

3.5 Progress Creating Integrated Macro Models

In parallel with this work, progress is also being made on a higher-level macro model, the kind of a model into which a number of mini models may one day be embedded.

This is still very much a work in progress and is explained in detail in D5.3 PoliRural Model (ed.3) available on the POLIRURAL project website.

The model is too complex to show diagrammatically on a single page. Suffice it to say that it consists of eight modules dealing with:

- Population,
- Education,
- Quality of life,
- Agriculture,
- Natural capital,
- Employment,
- Rural Attractiveness,
- Rural retention capacity.

Each of these modules already contains a lot of complexity. The model dealing with quality of life for examples is represented by the following diagram in STELLA (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Quality of life model made in STELLA

To complete the model each artifact and the links between them needs to be defined. Each contains elements of the dynamics of the system being modelled and must be defined by someone. This represents a lot of work and what has been achieved so far can of course be improved and may need to be adapted to better reflect the nature of the region and the goals of its specific Foresight exercise.

3.6 Organizing Regional Experiments in the Use of SDM in Foresight

3.6.1 Testing the Use of the SDM Macro-Model in Regional Foresight

The author of these models (Antoni Oliva of 22SISTEMA) is working with each of the regional Foresight teams, to help them understand the model and adapt it to their needs. Part of his work is to treat each model realization in each of the 12 regions of the POLIRURAL project, as a separate experiment in the use of SDM in Foresight.

On the basis of these interactions, each team is required to:

- Work to understand and improve the model,
- Define what they expect of the model in terms of
 - The dynamics or phenomena it is expected to clarify,
 - The group work with stakeholders it is expected to support.

The expected result of this work is a base model for each pilot, calibrated with real data from 2010 to 2020 (2014 – 2020 for the case of Galilee). The model will contain two baseline

scenarios: vegetative growth (where population growth or decline comes only from births and deaths); and BAU, where the dynamics observed in the last 10 years continue until 2040.

The regional teams are then expected to integrate these experiments into their Foresight process, for example in that part of the process where they focus on the development of the action plan, more specifically as part of the process for the development of future outlooks, as they are defined in this document.

3.6.2 Testing the Use of the Three Layer SDM Model in Regional Foresight

It is important to understand that these SDM tools have very little predictive power, and for the time being at least, their use should not be approached from this point of view. The expectation is that they will have value as learning tools to help stakeholders and others involve in making decision on complex issues, to

- better understand those issues,
- test policy mix in the model to see the mid- and long-term effects,
- participate more fully in the decision-making process, and
- thereby make better decisions.

In what follows, every reference to model is intended to include

- the three-layer diagram, accompanied by
- its intervention logic captured for example in the KDP matrix.

The suggested approach to experimenting with the use of such models is to:

- Define the expected gains from use of the model in terms of insight and understanding;
- Define the decisions that use of the model is expected to support;
- Share the alpha model with stakeholders and discuss the following:
 - the adequacy of the KPIs,
 - how well the Drivers-layer reflects the internal working of the economy,
 - how well the Policy options correspond to an adequate and effective policy intervention, and
 - how well the KDP matrix reflects the dynamics of the system.
- Suggest improvements and edit the diagram and KDP matrix to provide an update for sharing with colleagues outside the regional Foresight initiative.

Where available, test out the use of the beta-model, for example based on the following steps:

- Generate a list of policy options or scenarios amenable to investigation by the model,
- Compare the impact of those different policy scenarios on the KPIs,
- Note how the impact on KPIs evolves over time,
- Note how the measures might interact with each other,
- Discuss the concept of optimal policy scenario based on the model,
- Chose preferred policy scenarios that are optimal in some sense,
- Discuss how effective this exercise has been and propose improvements for the further development of the tool.

4 The Future Outlooks Methodology

Pulling all of this together, it is possible to outline the overall process for the development of the action plan, based on the exploration of Future Outlooks.

4.1 Preparatory Work

Task 1: Scout for local experts who can help you or with whom you can consult for the work of assembling lists of measures, KPIs and identifying relevant local data sets. They will be needed to help animate various stages in the process for developing the action plan. It is important to make sure that expert knowledge and understanding is available in these meetings. If not, the whole process will be at the mercy of people with little knowledge but lots of good intentions. The participation of these experts is essential for success, and so it is advisable to plan the meetings based on their availability. Other stakeholders who cannot make it to the meeting, can be consulted later. They can be informed of the outcomes and given opportunities to provide feedback later.

Task 2: Examine the list of challenges and for each challenge, make a preliminary list of policy measures and possible sources of financing. The “Inventory of Policy Options”, to be co-developed with the collaboration of all the regional Foresight teams, will provide a support for this work. Nevertheless, it is unlikely that this will contain an exhaustive list of policy options; Each team will still have to complete the list; ideally this can be done with the help of local experts and professionals in relevant departments of local administration.

Task 3: Define a preliminary list of KPIs, one list for each of the policy challenge. It is important that the concepts used are consistent with the SMART characterization of good indicators. In particular the indicators must be measurable, at last in principle and ideally data sets should be available to indicators, recent trends and current values of the indicators. Once more this is best done with the help of local experts, in particular those who have a good understanding of indicators and are able to help in sourcing the corresponding datasets.

4.2 The Engagement Process

The advantage of group work is that it provides a real sense of engagement and ownership on the part of those who take part. It also provides an important opportunity where stakeholders from different backgrounds can contribute with their own unique and timely perspectives. Given the constraints imposed by the pandemic, it is not possible to have the kind of group work session that are common in a Foresight exercise. Nevertheless, it is possible and so far, the regional Foresight teams have proven very capable in adaption to the situation and finding a good mixture of online and offline meeting formats, that permit the use of plenary and break out modes of working. This increases the burden of organization but so far has delivered good results.

The key tasks to perform in a group work format are as follows:

Task 4: Discuss the policy challenges with stakeholders, their associated KPIs and tentative targets. The discussion might lead to amendments or additions to these lists.

Task 5: Discuss the policy options. It might be useful to start with a preliminary list and complete it based on input from stakeholders. Use the discussion to check that the proposed work is adequately described. It may be necessary to qualify the initial descriptions of measure by adding conditions and other qualifications, with a view to ensuring its success and its coherence with the overall vision. In particular, clarify the intervention logic for each measure. It might help to use the logframe or elements of the logframe as a guide. But beware of generating more work for everyone than is useful.

Task 6: Develop “future outlooks” for each policy challenge. These are mixtures of policy options as described in the previous section. Depending on the burden of work and the time available, the regional team might decide to create these ambitions from basic documents such as the lists of challenges and policy options developed in the preliminary stage of work. Alternatively, they might develop tentative scenarios in advance of the meeting, intending that these be discussed by the stakeholders, working in plenary or break out mode or in some mixture of the two. As always, be ready and open to changes or additions. It is too early to make a selection. This will come later. For now, the focus is on making proposals.

Some of these tasks can be grouped and done together. Others need to be spaced out giving the stakeholders time to reflect, read, discuss with colleagues, and introduce new ideas if necessary.

Ideally the actors from public administration will get increasingly involved and the action plan takes shape as they start to undertake the role, they might have to play to make sure things get done later on.

Task 7: Experiment with the use of SDM to better understand the intervention logic, the interactions between different policy measures, the dynamics of change and how it unfolds over time, and how they all contribute to the KPIs over the entire period of time from the present until the landing point of the Foresight exercise, the year of the Foresight vision.

It will not be possible to treat all challenges or all measures in this way. The goal is to do this with a limited selection of challenges, or future outlooks, where the team has already developed some intuition by other means.

It will be of interest to see how these experiments work out. Hope with a confirmation of the potential for the use of such a tool, feedback on how it might best be used and insights it how the tool could be developed to enable such use in future.

Task 8: Select a future outlook for each challenge, which is “optimal” in some sense, and therefore a “preferred choice” for that part of the action plan intended to address each of the challenges. The collection of selected outlooks along with a narrative explaining how it was selected and in what sense it is considered to be the optimal choice, is the essentially the action plan for the realization of the vision.

When plenary sessions are organized, it is important to pay attention to who is in what group. Placing people with relevant expertise or experience or ownership of an issue in the same group. This is all part of the stakeholder engagement process.

Note that early implementation of a policy measure rarely consists of a full-scale roll-out. Usually, it must go through a series of phases through which the concept is demonstrated and proven, then validated, or calibrated until such time as a good understanding of the response of the economy and society to the measure is well understood. The overall dynamic might look something like the following:

- a feasibility study,
- a proof of concept or demonstration phase,
- a first pilot phase followed by a formal evaluation,
- a second pilot phase followed by a full-scale roll-out.

4.3 Relation to the Final Foresight Package

As a finale, it is now worth taking time out to visualize what is expected as an overall output of the regional Foresight exercise. The biggest challenge of implementation of a Foresight exercise, is to make sure that the process leads to action at some significant level, that it changes behaviours and ideally that it changes the nature of programming for regional growth and development.

For some practitioners, the goal of a Foresight exercise merely amounts to the construction of a vision. For others, the goal is to provide a focus for decisive action by public administration action, that will have a tangible and even transformative impact on the regional economy and society.

The need for such a significant transformation has never been greater. We now know that climate change is already happening, and that we need to act upon it. The EU ambition of achieving net zero by 2050, requires radical changes in the behaviour of citizens, in the way they live and work. Arguably, it is the most important driver of innovation in our time and will lead to the greatest industrial transformation in human history. It requires the complete integration of “natural capitals” into classical models of the economy. These issues have acquired increased urgency due to the major shocks of recent years. These include the financial crash of 2008, the sudden increase in catastrophic climate change vents of the last 5 years and the COVID pandemic of 2020. They include possible future shocks such as a recession due to the economic fallout of COVID-related lockdowns and the possibility of a brutal decline in biodiversity which puts the world’s food systems at risk.

Despite the general concentration of populations in cities, rural regions will play an increasingly important role in the overall sustainability of economic and social systems, as reservoirs of biodiversity and as providers of the raw materials and ecosystem services on which all depend.

Many of the ingredients needed to respond to this challenge are already in place. These include the Green Deal, the COVID recovery fund, the current wave of CAP reform and the new biodiversity strategy.

It is from this standpoint that we have opted for an approach to Foresight as a catalyst for the far-reaching transformation of rural regions. The general expectation is that each of the 12 regions of the project, will develop a linked “package” of three key documents (the vision, action-plan, and roadmap) that will be endorsed by major stakeholders of each region, and adopted by key actors in regional public administration who will ensure the execution of the overall program for growth and development.

Each of the twelve regional teams takes charge of the organization of the Foresight process and the development of these documents, in their own way, in consultation with their own stakeholders, subject to their own practical constraints, drawing upon the guidance provided in the project. This guidance includes:

- The STEEPV Inventory of Drives,
- The Guides to Deep Dives, and
- This methodology note, as well as
- The inventory of policy options.

The inventory of policy options will be co-developed in the coming months, based on collaboration involving the 12 regional teams. In what follows we provide guidance on the structure of the elements of the basic Foresight package.

4.3.1 The Vision

The vision is more than a simple statement. It is suggested that the vision contain the following elements:

- The vision statement;
- The list of policy challenges;
- A narrative explaining how these challenges were chosen, alternatives considered, and choices made and how these are expected to combine to realize the vision;
- The lists of KPIs associated with each of these challenges, indicating their current values, and targets to be achieved on the basis of the action plan.

4.3.2 The Action Plan

The role of the action plan is to explain what measures must be taken to address each of the policy challenges featuring in the vision. For each challenge one can include the following elements:

- Descriptions of each challenge;
- Lists of measures needed to address each challenge;
- Narratives outlining the intervention logic for each measure, explaining these are expected these to contribute to achieving the overall policy challenge.

4.3.3 The Roadmap

The role of the roadmap is to indicate the phasing of measures, assign responsibility for ensuring their delivery, and provide a good basis for the monitoring of progress over time. It is suggested that this includes the following main elements:

- The list of measures;
- The source of financing (regional, national or EU programs and mechanisms including PPPs);
- The phasing of the measure, and any relevant temporal constraint;
- The regional authority or authorities competent for designing the detailed measure, passing relevant legislation, and mobilizing the required resources.